

THE IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF COTTON IN UZBEKISTAN

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According to data, by 2050 the world population will exceed 9 billion people. In order to provide them with food, there will be an additional demand for the production of 1 billion tons of grain and more than 200 million tons of livestock products. As a result, new land will be acquired and the area of cultivated areas will increase dramatically. This will further increase the water shortage, which is becoming urgent. In particular, in the next 15 years, the shortage of water resources in the world may reach 40%. In this sense, it is worth saying that now the time demands the rational use of available resources in the water industry, the acceleration of irrigation and melioration measures, and the consistent implementation of cost-effective technologies in the system.

Based on this, certain works are being carried out in our country in this regard, that is, many works are being carried out with the aim of using modern technologies in the development of agriculture and water management. An example of this is the following decisions: In the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 is also included. That is, it is highlighted separately in the section 3.3 on the modernization and rapid development of agriculture of the priority direction of economic development and liberalization [1].

Based on these decisions, the following priority tasks for the development of cotton farming in the Republic of Uzbekistan to be implemented in 2019 were adopted:

- It was decided to strictly follow the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 22, 2018 No. 1037, to prevent the planting of more than 5 varieties in one region and 2 in one district.
- In order to improve the melioration condition of 419.7 thousand hectares of saline areas and to create a moisture reserve in the soil, once in 188.9 thousand hectares, twice in 176.3 thousand hectares and three times in 54.6 thousand hectares will be carried out.

Based on the capacity of chemical enterprises, 103 thousand 350 tons of physical cotton for feeding 1 - May 1, 434 thousand 110 tons for feeding 2 - until June 1, and 206 thousand 720 tons of nitrogen for feeding 3 - until July 10 a reserve of mineral fertilizers is created.

- The management and service system of agricultural water resources will be improved. Based on the available water resources, the development of water supply according to the type of crop and the complete supply of water to the farm located in the last ear will be ensured until the end of the season.
- Measures will be taken to fully engage the 1400 cotton picking machines in the republic.
- 37.5 thousand hectares of cotton cultivation areas with low productivity and poor land reclamation conditions will be reduced and replaced by export-oriented food crops. thousand hectares (33%), 60 cm. In the scheme, 480 thousand hectares (46%) and 76 cm. In the scheme, 69.3 thousand hectares (7 %) and 90 cm. 145.9 thousand hectares (14%) of seeds are planted in the scheme.

In comparison to 2018, sowing of seeds in the "double" method will be increased by 27.3 thousand hectares, the average productivity will increase by 0.5-1.0 centner per hectare, and the efficiency of material resources and mechanization services will be increased by 10-15%.

- In 2019, 64 cotton-textile production clusters planned to cultivate cotton on an area of about 520,000 hectares. It was also decided to increase cotton raw material production to at least 52% by the cotton-textile cluster method.
- Water-saving technologies (drip irrigation) will be introduced on 20 thousand hectares by newly established clusters and farms.
- The volume of use of plant growth correctors, which have the feature of increasing the yield and quality of cotton in cotton fields, will be increased.
- In 2019, the guaranteed state purchase price of raw cotton will be 4 million soums per ton or 23% higher than last year. The term of preferential loans will be extended from 14 to 17 months.

Today, drip irrigation method stands out among the modern irrigation methods. In this irrigation method, water is given not to the soil, but to the root part of the plant, which serves to reduce the consumption of water for crops. At the same time, it serves to increase the yield of crops. It should be noted that the advantage of drip irrigation technologies is not only in saving water. This method of irrigation is effective in improving land reclamation and achieving a high yield. For example, during drip irrigation, water is evenly distributed throughout the field in accordance with the needs of each crop in a certain period. As a result, soil moisture is provided at the same rate. since the fertilizer is given with water, there is no need to use equipment for fertilizing. Also, the rate of assimilation of the nutrients given to the crop in this way is high. Experts

say that it has been proven in practice that the productivity of drip-irrigated gardens and vineyards increases by 40%, and by 60% in cotton and vegetable fields.

Advantages of using a modern system of drip irrigation:

- A large amount of water saving - only the root part of the plant gets wet, the amount of water wasted by evaporation decreases. The water consumption for one hectare of grass in drip irrigation is 3.5 thousand meters ³, 5-5.5 thousand m³ or 60-65 percent of water is saved.
- Electricity, labor costs, fuel-lubrication (FOLL) and lubrication and other materials are saved. As a result of less water required in drip irrigation, less electricity or diesel fuel is used for the operation of pumps, per 1 ha of cotton area, labor cost for irrigation is saved 2.5-3 times by 80-85 liters.
- 30-40 percent use of mineral fertilizers - 800 kg of nitrogen fertilizer, 150 kg of phosphorus, 100 kg of potassium per 1 hectare of cotton area in normal irrigation, 250-300 kg of nitrogen in drip irrigation, 150 kg of phosphorus, 50 kg of potassium are used. The absorption of mineral fertilizers is 90-95 percent, and in traditional irrigation it is 30-38 percent. Fertilizers dissolved during watering enter the root zone directly and nutrients are quickly absorbed. This is the most effective method of fertilizing.
- High yield and quality of the product - early ripening of the crop is observed in drip irrigation. The yield is 50-55% higher compared to traditional irrigation due to the clear entry of moisture into the plant system and complete absorption of fertilizers. .
- It is possible to irrigate land areas with different water absorption into the soil and very uneven surfaces, the drip irrigation system is located in the furrows and allows watering without moving the soil.
- Between the rows, the soil will be dry throughout the season, and it will be convenient for the movement of equipment and people during agro technical activities.
- The number of weeds is low, because the water is delivered to the root system of the plant, the surrounding land is not irrigated, the cotton root develops well and many active root hairs are formed, water and nutrients the rate of consumption increases.

The modern system of drip irrigation has both advantages and disadvantages, examples of which are as follows:

- High construction costs;
- High demand for water quality, need for cleaning;

- Failure to improve the microclimate;
- Rapid failure of polymer pipes;
- Pressure requirement;
- In order to widely apply drip irrigation, first of all, it is necessary to reduce the salinity level of the land and reduce the turbidity of the water, etc.

In our country, efforts are being made to explain the advantages of modern irrigation methods to farm managers. In this regard, the mass media in our country are also working organically. In the Republic, saving water resources and obtaining high and stable yields from irrigated areas has been raised to the level of state policy. Based on the address of our Honorable President to the Supreme Assembly dated December 28, 2018, a wide range of activities were carried out in connection with the decree on the organization of educational seminars for the improvement of knowledge and skills of farm managers [2]. The professor-teachers of "Water management and melioration" department, TIAME Bukhara branch visited Bukhara, Navoi, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions of our republic and together with industry experts conducted educational seminars for the managers of farms. The main purpose of these seminars is to further increase the knowledge of farm managers and to use land and water resources wisely by applying modern resource-efficient technologies in irrigated lands.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that by using modern irrigation technologies in irrigated areas, not only water resources, but also labor force, increase of work productivity, improvement of land reclamation condition, improvement of the quality of harvested crops, etc. are achieved. By using only modern irrigation technologies, 0.8 billion m³ in 2022 and 1.6 billion m³ in 2030 will be saved. This has a positive effect on our economy.

List of used literature:

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